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Aggregation of binary mixtures of sodium deoxycholate and sodium cholate in aqueous solutions with the addition of 6% propanol and 6% isopropanol

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Sodium dexycolate (SD) and sodium cholate (SC), above a certain (total) concentration (cmcmM), in aqueous solution form binary mixed micelles. It is already known that, in the temperature interval $T = (278.15 - 298.15)$ there are synergistic interactions between SD and SC, in their mixed micelles. [1]. In this research, effects of adding 6% (v/v) propanol and 6% (v/v) isopropanol to aqueous solutions of SD and SC, mixed in different molar ratios ($\alpha = 0, 0.2, 0.5, 0.8$ and 1), were examined regarding the critical micelle concentration values (cmc), at different temperatures (278.15 K, 283.15 K, 288.15 K, 293.15 K, 298.15 K, 303.15 K and 308.15 K). Both additives reduced the cmc values of SD and SC in their aqueous solution. Mixed micelles of SD and SC also had reduced the cmcmM values in aqueous solutions which contained propanol and isopropanol additives, compared to their cmcmM values in aqueous solution without additives. The cmc values of SD were lower in aqueous solutions with 6% isopropanol than in aqueous solutions with 6% propanol, at all temperatures. As for SC, there were no significant difference in its cmc values between the propanol-containing solutions and the isopropanol-containing solutions, at all temperatures. In the binary mixed micelles having 20% and 80% molar ratios of DC, the cmcmM values were lower in aqueous solutions with 6% propanol than in aqueous solutions with 6% isopropanol, at all temperatures. In the mixed micelles with 50% molar ratio of DC, the cmcmM values were higher in aqueous solutions with 6% propanol than in aqueous solutions with 6% isopropanol, at all temperatures. The size, shape and aggregation number of the examined mixed micelles should be investigated by small angle neutron scattering, in order to further explain the obtained results.

References

- [1] Poša M, Pilipovic A. Effects of additives (methanol and NaCl) from aqueous surfactant solutions on the micellisation of sodium deoxycholate and sodium cholate binary mixture in the temperature interval $T = (278.15-318.15)$ K: The molar excess Gibbs energy and the molar Gibbs energy of the micelle formation. *The Journal of Chemical Thermodynamics*. 2020; 150:106179.